

Article

Spanish Tipsters and the Millennial and Centennial Generations in the Scenario of a Pandemic

Almudena Barrientos-Báez¹, Juan Enrique González-Vallés^{1,*}, José Daniel Barquero-Cabrero², and David Caldevilla-Domínguez¹

¹ Faculty of Information Science, Complutense University of Madrid, Spain

² Research Department, ESERP Business & Law School, Spain

* Corresponding author (jegonzalvez@ucm.es)

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Abstract

The growth and popularization of sports betting have led to the emergence of a new type of influencer: Tipsters, people and betting houses who influence and advise through social networks on the bets they consider most profitable. Both agents are also content-generating, forming a particular ecosystem with a specific narrative. The research examines the narratives of both the personal and betting houses profiles that make up the category of tipsters and their impact on younger generations. It also takes an in-depth look at the content and languages used by tipsters on social media and what determines their success in terms of followers and interactions. The period and place analyzed is the year 2020 in Spain, because it allows observing the differences between the periods of free transit and the quarantine period caused by Covid-19. The selection of the studied profiles is based on the five most recommended profiles, according to 10 rankings in the sports betting sector. The results show how the tipsters' narrative was adapted to the context of the pandemic to maintain interest during the quarantine and not lose its influence towards millennials and centennials. Especially relevant is the period after the quarantine, with long periods of stay at home by young people, where the narrative has iconic, symbolic, and linguistic elements typical of war periods.

Keywords

centennial generation; gambling; generation Z; millennial generation; pandemic; social networks; tipsters

Issue

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1. Introduction

1.1. New Generations, Consumption Habits, and Use of Influencers

According to García-Marín (2021) and Martín Critikián and Medina Núñez (2021), there are four clearly differentiated types of consumer generations: Baby Boomers (1945–1964); Generation X (1965–1980); Millennials (1981–1994); and Generation Z or centennials (1995–2010). The most frequently employed digital

trends for Baby Boomers are email, television, as well as print media. As for the social networks used most frequently in this generation, they are Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn. Second, for Generation X, the media in which they mainly move are email, radio, and in terms of the most used social networks, Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram stand out. Third, for millennials there is a change compared to the two previous generations, since the media in which they are found are mainly digital, having as reference social networks Facebook, YouTube, and Instagram. Finally, Generation Z, they are found both on

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About the Authors

Almudena Barrientos-Báez is a PhD with international mention cum laude in education. She is a doctoral assistant at the Complutense University of Madrid. She was director of the qualifying MA in Teacher Training at the European University of Madrid. She holds a MA in Management of Protocol, Production, Organization, and Design of Events—communication area—at the Universidad Camilo José Cela, and a MA in management of tourist accommodation at the Universitat Girona. She has a degree in tourism (EUTI–ULL) and teaching (Universitat de València).

Juan Enrique González-Vallés holds a PhD in information sciences from the Complutense University of Madrid. He has a degree in journalism. He currently belongs to the Department of Theories and Analysis of Communication at the Complutense University of Madrid where he lectures on research methods in advertising and public relations, psychology of communication, and hypermedia narrative. He holds the accreditation of Associate Professor by ANECA. Previously, he belonged to the Department of Audiovisual Communication and Advertising at CEU San Pablo University.

José Daniel Barquero-Cabrero is a professor, as well as a PhD, in the area of economic and social sciences from the International University of Catalonia. He also received a PhD from Camilo José Cela University of Madrid, Autonomous University of Coahuila de México, and the universities of Malaga, Huelva, Cádiz and Seville (interuniversity PhD). He has been awarded, for his contributions to the academic world, the title of doctor honoris causa by universities in America, Europe, and Asia.

David Caldevilla-Domínguez is a BA and PhD of information sciences (audiovisual communication from the Complutense University). He has a diploma in teaching (University of Zaragoza). He is a professor at the Faculty of Information Sciences of the Complutense University of Madrid. He teaches at the Complutense University of Madrid, Universidad Europea de Madrid, IED, ESERP, and IPAM. He has an h-index of 19, if the sixth Spanish author in published works, the 13th in cited articles, and 20th in citations received from 747 total authors.